

DEVELOPMENT AND IMPROVEMENT OF SPEED ABILITIES IN 11–12-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS

U.A.Saidov

Lecturer at Gulistan State University

I.Y.Mavlonov

Student of the 1–24 group in Sports Activity (Volleyball)

Annotation: *This article highlights the factors that develop and improve the speed abilities of modern 11–12-year-old football players.*

Keywords: *physical qualities, physical training, technical and tactical preparation.*

Ключевые слова: *Young players, quickness, physical qualities.*

Relevance of the Study: The insufficient development of speed abilities in young football players negatively affects their performance in football. Improving speed qualities enhances athletes' results.

Purpose of the Study: The study is aimed at increasing the functional capabilities of young football players, developing their physical abilities comprehensively, and improving speed, agility, and other physical qualities.

Objectives of the Study: -The research includes the following tasks: -Analysis of the development of modern football; -Study of theory, methods, and techniques for developing speed in young football players; -Designing annual training plans and improving sports mastery during training sessions.

Modern football is continuously evolving, and playing techniques and player movements are becoming more refined. The emergence of new and effective techniques requires players to perform movements at a high level. During a match, each player performs numerous actions to help the team win.

The main movements of football players include: walking, running, running with the ball, dribbling, jumping, shooting, feints, passing, ball control, throw-ins, free kicks, corner kicks, tackling, accurate targeting, and competing for the ball.

Developing the physical qualities of young football players is one of the key aspects of sports training. Physical qualities are connected with the morphological, physiological, and biological characteristics of the body. They positively influence technical-tactical readiness and psychological-emotional state.

Players perform movements more confidently, learn new skills faster, and achieve higher performance levels. Modern football demands high physical preparedness, with speed being one of the most important qualities.

The development of speed is linked to:

- Enhancing functional capabilities of young players;
- Analyzing modern football development and scientific-methodological aspects;
- Identifying ways to improve speed in young footballers;

- Planning annual training and improving performance.

Research Results: The study showed that during training sessions, exercises performed with the ball accounted for 87% to 93%, while exercises without the ball made up 7% to 12%.

During a 10-month training period: 31.9 hours were devoted to speed development, which is about 8.2% of total training time;

Time allocated to speed and speed-strength training was nearly equal.

Analysis also showed: Total sprint distance during matches: 4840 meters; With the ball: 1860 meters (38.4%); Without the ball: 2890 meters (61.6%).

This confirms the importance of including non-specific exercises in training.

For 12-year-old players:

In training: 5 m sprints: 45.5% , 10 m sprints: 32.8%

In matches: 5 m sprints: ~60% , 10 m: 24.7% , 15 m: 10%

This shows that speed activity changes from training to competition.

During matches: Total sprint distance: ~110 m , With the ball: 38 m , Without the ball: 60 m , Number of sprints: 13.1 times , With ball: 5.1 , Without ball: 8.0 , Most sprints occur over distances of 5–15 meters., During a 1-hour training session: Average sprint volume: 135.2 meters (relatively low). Jump training results: Optimal drop height: 35 cm , Vertical and depth jumps (20 cm, 40 cm, 60 cm): 54.3 cm, 56.4 cm, 54.4 cm . Jump speed remained stable (226.9 m/s and 224.9 m/s).

It was observed that muscle contraction time slightly decreases during jumping.

Training Recommendations: The most effective method for developing speed in young players is the “shock” (plyometric) method; It includes depth jumps followed by vertical or long jumps; Two “shock” training sessions per day are recommended;

In a 1-hour session, this method should not exceed 15–20 minutes.

Conclusion: Modern football requires high physical fitness, especially speed development. The ages of 11–12 are considered a crucial period for developing these qualities.

Literature analysis shows that young football players may have lower speed readiness compared to athletes in other sports. Therefore, this age is one of the most important stages for developing speed.

Adjusting training volume, methods, and tools during this period leads to positive improvements in training outcomes.

REFERENCES:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We Will Build a Free and Prosperous Democratic Uzbekistan Together. Tashkent, 2016.
2. Presidential Decree No. PQ-3610 (March 16, 2018) on Football Development Measures.

3. Presidential Decree No. PF-5887 (December 4, 2019) on Advancing Football Development in Uzbekistan.
4. Axmadjonov U.M., Tolibjonov A.I., Isyeev Sh.T. Physical Training of Football Players. 2019.
5. Kuznetsov A.A. Football: A Handbook for Youth Coaches. Moscow, 2008.
6. Platonov V.N. System of Athlete Preparation in Olympic Sports. Kyiv.
7. Kuramshin Y.F. Problems of modernization of physical education. St. Petersburg, 2011.
8. Pashenko L.G. et al. Modern educational technologies in physical education. Moscow, 2014.
9. Pashenko L.G. Parental attitudes toward family physical education. 2014.